

IZMIR UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
DEPARTMENT OF AEROSPACE ENGINEERING

Autonomous Optical and Inertial Navigation with iPhone 11 and DSLR Camera of a Realistic Solar Sail Propelled CubeSat Class Spacecraft Targeting Orbits around Mars and its Moons

Author: Kıymet Yıldır

Supervisor: Dr. Fabrizio Pinto

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Kıymet Yıldır

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Abstract

This thesis focuses on autonomous optical navigation. The study analyzed the convergence of observations and planned activities by designing the iPhone 11 camera and Nikon D3100 DSLR camera as a spacecraft and simulating the rotation of the Earth to increase the realism of optical navigation. By understanding rotation errors, this thesis focuses on achieving more precise positioning of the spacecraft. With respect to calculations that were gathered from observations, the relative error in magnitude is 0.000017, by this calculation this method can work. Research into improved autonomous optical navigation is becoming a key aspect of modern space missions. The growing demand for the Deep Space Network (DSN) poses challenges for all missions. At the same time, the fascination with space exploration is increasing due to the inherent mysticism and inherent difficulty of observation. As space missions become increasingly important this century, Earth-based navigation is becoming increasingly complex. Autonomous navigation, which is crucial for these missions, requires continuous development. The advent of solar sail technology is proving to be a key component of space missions. This technology enables high-speed movement without traditional propulsion methods, overcoming the challenges of heavy fuel tanks. In summary, the article highlights the importance of developing autonomous navigation for space exploration in the context of scalable space missions. While trying to make it happen in the paper, Wolfram Mathematica, ASTAP, Stellarium, DeepSkyStacker, and Astrometry.net were used.

1 List of Symbols

ASTAP Astrometric Stacking Program by hnsky.org. 4, 15, 16, 39

AutoNav Autonomous Navigation System. 13, 16, 26

AutOpNav Autonomous Optical Navigation System. 20, 21

CCD Charge-coupled device. Major technology used in digital imaging. 3, 23–25

DS1 Deep Space 1. 13

DSLR Digital single-lens reflex. 3, 21, 26, 40

DSN Deep Space Network, is the network of spacecraft communication ground antennas which are located in the United States, Spain and Australia to support spacecraft missions to interplanetary and deep space missions. 8, 9, 17, 69

DSS DeepSkyStacker. It is a software for stacking images. 3, 24, 27–29, 34, 35, 55, 58, 59

ecliptic The ecliptic plane refers to the planet’s orbit in which the Earth revolves around the Sun. 9, 10

FORTRAN Fortran is a compiled, imperative, and versatile programming language particularly suitable for numerical and scientific computing. 10

FOSS Free Open Source Software. 15, 26, 27, 39, 40

FOV Field of view. 24

FPA First Point of Aries: The position where the celestial equator circle and the ecliptic circle intersection is the zero point for the right ascension. It marks the moment when the Sun enters the northern hemisphere at the start of spring (the vernal equinox). 9, 14, 15

heliocentric Heliocentric model is a model that the Sun is at the center and planets are rotating around it. 9, 10, 14

IAU International Astronomical Union. 11

ICRF International Celestial Reference Frame. 9, 41, 42

JPL Jet Propulsion Laboratory. 26, 51

JupyterNotebook It is a tool that may be used in a variety of industries and is the most recent web-based dynamic application software for algorithms and data. 26, 41

LOS Imaginary line between the observer and the target. 21

OpNav Optical Navigation. 16, 17

RA-DEC Right ascension and declination, often known as longitude and latitude for the astronomy and used to indicate where an object appears among the stars and constellations, are abbreviated as RA and DEC. 27, 39, 51

solar-sail Solar sails are a type of spacecraft propulsion system that makes use of the radiation pressure imposed by sunlight on wide mirrors. 69

topocentric Topocentric model uses the celestial coordinates of a specific point on the surface of the Earth. 10, 14

2 Introduction

Even in normal people's lives, navigation systems are irreplaceable. This system will also play an important role in the near and distant future because in the future people will still need a navigation system to get to a new place. For this reason, navigation systems are used all over the world. Navigation systems are used, for example, in automobiles, submarines, and commercial aircraft. Space is another discipline that uses navigation systems. The Deep Space Network (DSN) is currently used for most spacecraft. Take advantage of this network, whether it is the satellites launched in the 1960s or the International Space Station in orbit. However, in recent years the number of spacecraft launches has increased significantly, resulting in an ever-increasing load on the DSN network. In addition to the DSN overhead, spacecraft intended to fly long distances may struggle with the effectiveness of this system due to the limited speed of light. For these reasons, new navigation systems have begun to emerge. One way to navigate in space is to use an optical navigation system. The optical navigation system could be able to become independent of the DSN and, using onboard systems, independently determine the spacecraft's position, its distance to other planets or asteroids, and its angle relative to the Sun. This system also exists to increase the spacecraft's independence to nearly triple digits by combining it with a solar sail propulsion system. If this system is automated in the future, it will go down in history as one of the most important steps towards space travel. In this project, the software developed by Ahmet Orhun Sivaslı, Burak Köse, and Ekin Gürhan([6]), was used to calculate the spacecraft's position with respect to images taken by me. With this method, the real error can be calculated in the optical autonomous navigation system. Also, as a three-group, the total work of this project was done. In group 2, Hayriye Memiş, Dogukan Coşkun, and Eilf Gökyolcu did a digital twin of the CubeSat [14]. In group 3, Muratcan Yurttaş, Sıla Simay Mumcuoğlu, and Bora Atakan did the trajectory of the spacecraft [15].

3 Literature Review

3.1 A.Roy,"Orbital Motion"(2005) [1]

Navigation systems play an important role in interplanetary missions. Navigation in space missions can be controlled by two methods and sub-methods within these two methods.

The first method is an earth-controlled navigation system. Optical positioning can be used as a secondary method of land navigation. This method involves monitoring the spacecraft using specific instruments, such as telescopes in ob-

servatories. The main problem with this method is that it becomes increasingly difficult to see the spacecraft the further it gets from Earth. Once the spacecraft has flown far enough, it becomes invisible to the observer. As for the second sub-method, radar observations are used, mainly using DSN. But the overload on the DSN becoming a huge problem.

The second method employs the same methodology on a spaceship. Onboard optical navigation, for example, can be accomplished by simply constructing a camera to examine the spacecraft's surroundings. These systems typically employ the coordinate system, which is already known and determined by a number of characteristics, such as the positions of stars, planets, and other celestial objects at a given time. If the perturbations caused by gravitational influences, radiation, and air drag (for Earth orbiter spacecraft) are taken into account during navigation, the spacecraft's orbit may be computed for all epochs. As a result, the spacecraft's velocity and acceleration may also be computed.

There are many coordinate systems in spatial navigation, which are explained in the following sections. However, for convenience, Roy uses J2000/ICRF to perform the calculations.

Generally, the planned route to the destination differs from the actual route during the mission due to interference. Maneuvers during the mission can correct the spacecraft's trajectory for any disturbances.

The Roy approach that was used in the project is based on the position corners of the spacecraft. For ease of understanding, it maintains its basic approach and uses three objects with known locations. The three objects are the spaceship, the sun, and the beacon. The heliocentric ecliptic cartesian using the first Aries point (FPA) is assumed as the coordinate system. The heliocentric coordinates of the spacecraft's ecliptic can be calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \arctan \left(\frac{Y}{X} \right) \text{Degrees} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = \arctan \left(\frac{Z}{\sqrt{X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2}} \right) \text{Degrees} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: The Model of Optical Navigation (Sketched via diagrams.net)[1]

With these calculations, Archie Roy obtains the topocentric ecliptic Coordinates of the beacon (can be an asteroid, planet or star) as seen by the spacecraft. It is possible to calculate the topocentric celestial coordinates (RA and Dec) of the beacons.

Let's assume the opposite if the spacecraft's heliocentric ecliptic coordinates hold are known at time t and from the observations it is possible to calculate the heliocentric cartesian coordinates of the spacecraft. However, the problem with this approach lies in the accuracy of the calculations. However, to increase the accuracy of this approach, you can increase the number of beacons.

3.2 J. Meeus, "Astronomical Algorithms" (1998) [2]

As the author indicates, this book is aimed at researchers interested in astronomical calculations in programming languages such as FORTRAN. All calculations were adapted to the J2000 standard.

Before explaining coordinate transformations, it was necessary to refer to Chapter 1 of Meeus, which talks about choosing the correct quadrant of the coordinate system. As known if the sine, cosine, tangent, or cotangent angle is known, can be easily calculated the angle using their inverse trigonometric function. Because inverse trigonometric functions have different values for the four cardinal quadrants of the coordinate system, calculating the exact angle value can be difficult. To do this different programming languages can be used. However, most of them do not contain a function to calculate them. However, the Meeus expression

to calculate these angles can be used to determine the required function for the programming language that is used. While this is explained in later chapters of the report, the example provided by Meeus is as follows:

For example, for both $\cos 147^\circ$ and $\cos 213^\circ$ the answer is same : -0.8387. So, with that example, the importance of choosing the right quadrant can be understood.

Therefore, when using inverse trigonometric functions, blur appears, which is necessary and must be solved to get accurate results.

It should be noted that Meeus does not follow the IAU resolution but accepts the longitudes as positive. Longitudes are measured positively westward because this approach can be used for multiple planets. Therefore, its central meridian from Earth increases over time.

$$\tan \lambda = \frac{\sin \alpha \cos \epsilon + \tan \delta \sin \epsilon}{\cos \alpha} \quad (3)$$

$$\sin \beta = \sin \delta \cos \epsilon - \cos \delta \sin \epsilon \sin \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\sin \lambda \cos \epsilon - \tan \beta \sin \epsilon}{\cos \lambda} \quad (5)$$

$$\sin \delta = \sin \beta \cos \epsilon + \cos \beta \sin \epsilon \sin \lambda \quad (6)$$

The above equations explain the relationship between celestial coordinates and ecliptic coordinates, where ϵ is the slope of the ecliptic.

Meeus also mentions time conventions in Chapter 10. Universal Time (UT) is based on the rotation of the Earth. The UT is used in daily life to determine work and study times. The UT must also be taken into account for astronomical observations based on local time. Most browsers generally use UT instead of GMT. However, this does not apply to astronomical observations as GMT and UT differ by 12 hours. As the Earth's rotation speed decreases, UT is no longer a consistent time for astronomers. Therefore, a new time scale called ephemeris time, called dynamic time, was established and uses atomic clocks to determine it. Due to the relativistic effect of the Sun resulting from the motion of the Earth in orbit, there is a difference between dynamic barycentric time (TDB) and terrestrial dynamic time (TDT) of at most 0.0017 seconds. Since this error is negligible in practice, the two times are called dynamic times or "TD" for short. The difference between TD and UT can only be calculated based on observations.

$$\Delta T = TD - UT \quad (7)$$

$$t = \frac{\text{year} - 2000}{100} \quad (8)$$

Where ΔT is in seconds t is the time measured in J2000 reference system.
For example for year 948 the equation is :

$$\Delta T = 2177 + 497t + 44.1t^2 \quad (9)$$

For the year between 948 and 1600, and after 2000 the equation become :

$$\Delta T = 102 + 102t + 25.3t^2 \quad (10)$$

However, to avoid a discontinuity in 2000, the following corrections should be made:

$$+0.37 \times (\text{year} - 2100) \quad (11)$$

So, equation 11 can be applied for the years between 2000 to 2100.
More examples are available in the book. Anyone interested can check.

3.3 J.E. Riedel et al, ” Autonomous Optical Navigation (AutoNav) Technology Validation Report” (2000) [3]

In 2000, on February 8, J. E. Riedel and his DS1 navigation team members of the AutoNav and RadioNav teams release a report on the DS1 mission, the first mission of NASA’s New Millennium program. In this report, Riedel and colleagues discuss DS1’s important mission, focusing on navigation system technology. The report discusses navigation system development, technology dependencies, ground and flight testing, AutoNav challenges in the current DS1 mission, and future applications of AutoNav in future missions. DS1 mission was the first optically autonomous system deployed in deep space. AutoNav uses images of nearby celestial objects, such as asteroids, against distant celestial objects and stars to determine geometric properties through parallax. This information is then used in a dynamic filter to compute the main navigational parameters of the spacecraft, coordinates and velocity vectors, and other parameters such as the performance of the ion propulsion system (IPS) and solar radiation pressure. These calculations are carried out by the integrated software using various functions. For DS1, the key features of AutoNav were NavRT, NavExec, ImageProcessor, OD, and ManeuverPlanner. The purpose of each of these functions was to provide navigation-relevant information to other subsystems, to perform navigation-related tasks such as taking images of asteroids, processing those images, determining an orbit from those images, and planning maneuvers and necessary corrections. As with any space technology demonstration mission, AutoNav encountered numerous difficulties shortly after DS1’s launch in October 1998. Firstly, there was a serious light leak problem in the DS1 imaging system, where the light was scattered due to sunlight reflected from the satellite from the spaceship body. This problem significantly limited the camera’s ability to detect asteroids because the lens absorbed too much light from the spacecraft’s body, making the asteroids less detectable. In addition, data collected after the launch showed that the camera had geometric distortions in the camera field that were much larger than expected before the launch. Despite all these difficulties, J.E. Riedel et al. report that although the estimated errors due to these conditions were 1000 km and 7 m/s, this was still sufficient for an interplanetary mission. Although the error was sufficient due to non-ideal conditions distorting the results, the team quickly updated the software to compensate for these conditions and was able to further reduce the error to about 250 km and 0.2 m/s in February 1999. Overall, this report provides a lot of details about AutoNav as well as technical details. Thanks to the results and problems of the DS1, important data could be collected for future AutoNav applications.

3.4 F. Pinto, "Element of Optical Navigation" (2022) [4]

Fabrizio Pinto uses the Roy[1] and Meeus[2] approach to determine this topocentric positions of beacon asteroids when the heliocentric Cartesian positions of asteroids and spacecraft are known, and calls this method the direct problem. He then continues his calculations with the inverse problem, that is, from this data we know the celestial coordinates of the asteroids seen by the spacecraft and the coordinates of the solar ecliptic to determine the position of the spacecraft. He and his former student, Hazal Karaaliler et al.[5], at Izmir University of Economics, have done remarkable work despite significant errors. Fabrizio Pinto created the following images showing the positions of the asteroids (10) Hygiea and (944) Hidalgo. (See also [16])

Figure 2: (10) Hygiea Position Correction respect to FPA

Figure 3: (944) Hidalgo Position Correction respect to FPA

3.5 Karaaliler et al. , “Autonomous optical and inertial navigation of solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft during targeting missions to asteroids and minor moons.” (2022) [5]

Hazal Karaaliler and his team have set the goal for the 2021-2022 academic year to prove the concept of the optical navigation model. However, to accomplish such a feat, his team had to start from scratch and lay out the astrophotography requirements for obtaining the astrometric data.

Imaging devices are essential for optical navigation in space. In theory, a simple onboard camera can effectively measure astrometric data in space. As with any measuring device, calibration of the equipment is essential. This is exactly where Hazal Karaaliler and his team come in by putting together calibration frames: dark, bias, and flat field frames. Each calibration image must be taken multiple times to average the expected noise on the camera sensor.

These calibration images are then fed into a range of software, all of which are FOSS or free. First, DeepSkyStacker is used to stack and create “master frames,” including the “master light frame.” Additional alignment and stacking of these frames is performed to create the final “scientific frame.” Once a calibrated image has been obtained, it is possible to start photometric and astrometric calculations using another free software, ASTAP. Together with ASTAP, Astrometry.net, an astrometric calibration and analysis web service for astronomical images, is used to verify the accuracy of the central pixel coordinate of the scientific framework.

By making the necessary adjustments via ASTAP, they were able to use the Blink method to detect and get a first approximation of the asteroid's pixel coordinates. Additionally, they used the Blink method to create an MPC-80 file that was fed into the FindOrb app to find the orbit. At this point, Hazal Karaaliler and his team decided to increase the precision of their asteroid measurements by analyzing the asteroids' subpixels and applying the point spread function to address the stretching and blurring that occurs due to device limitations of images. Thus, Hazal Karaaliler and her team obtained a good approximation of the data collected by the Urla, Izmir imaging teams and completed their work by applying the navigation model to certain large asteroids.

In this case, their work is invaluable since the decision was made to adopt the same OpNav model that its predecessors had stopped at. Their work laid the foundation and allowed the team and its successors to focus on automating the process of navigation calculations for position acquisition. This allows the user to integrate as many asteroids as desired and measure and investigate numerous error modes within the navigation model to reduce the error rate as much as possible. Thanks to his work, it was possible to understand the process of obtaining coordinates from amateur astrophotography hardware and freely available software.

3.6 Sivash et al. , "Autonomous Optical and Inertial Navigation of a Solar-sail Propelled CubeSat Class Spacecraft Targeting Mars and its Moons" (2023) [6]

Ahmet Orhan Sivashlı and his team continued the path that Hazal Karaaliler and her team started. They combined both Roy's AutoNav model and Meeus's approach to choosing the right quarter of the coordinate system. They developed software that calculates the error of the position of the spacecraft and the asteroid. Also, the software can show the positions on the coordinate system, too. For those calculations, they used Fabrizio Pinto's direct and indirect problem statement.

They used JPL's Horizons System for taking the celestial data of asteroids. After taking the data they were able to make the calculations by comparing them with the originals. They used Wolfram Free Engine Mathematica for their software and calculations and also had a simulation output where the asteroids are from AstroGrav.

There is a reference frame problem with the Horizons System, heliocentric celestial coordinates are with respect to the J2000 reference frame, but for the observations particularly topocentric celestial coordinates are with respect to on date reference frame. They added their software some equations for that problem and they were able to reduce the error with these equations.

With their software error system calculation, real error calculations can be done. In this thesis, the main purpose to take images and can be able to calculate the error of a real camera. Some images going to be taken with a phone camera which can be suitable for a small CubeSat. After that, the celestial coordinates of the object are going to be calculated from images and going to be put into the software that Ahmet Orhun Sivaslı and his teammates developed. With that system, a real error from a real camera can be calculated.

3.7 E. Sahr et al. , ” Post-Launch Characterization of the Optical Navigation Instruments For Nasa’s Lucy Mission” (2022) [7]

The Lucy spacecraft was launched in October 2021 and is designed to explore asteroids in the Trojan regions on the surface of Jupiter; The duration of the mission is stated to be 12 years. These Trojan regions are called “L4” and “L5”. The spacecraft is estimated to reach the L4 region in June 2027. By November 2028, the plan is to study asteroids passing five different asteroids in this region. If the spacecraft leaves the L4 Trojan region for the L5 region after a planned five-year flight, the mission will be considered successful because sufficient data will be collected by studying the asteroids.

Normally, the Lucy spacecraft would require a lot of fuel to complete this long-range, long-duration mission. For going to be able to go some deep space, without a high volume of fuel, it was decided that it would be worthwhile to use Earth’s gravity. To reach the desired regions, the orbit must be adjusted accordingly, and the Lucy spacecraft will achieve this by coming very close to Earth. In this way, thanks to this maneuver, the ship can complete its journey without having too much fuel on board. However, an additional engine has been added to the spacecraft on Lucy’s ground to avoid the crowded Earth orbit, and plans are to turn it on to prevent Lucy from colliding with satellites as it enters Earth’s orbit. Lucy will fly close to these asteroids during the mission to obtain high-quality results. In addition, Lucy, using the DSN as usual, will also use OpNav as a navigation system to precisely navigate the spacecraft. Since a state-of-the-art, sensitive navigation system is required to ensure close flight of the spacecraft, detailed visual measurements are taken, as optical navigation systems require an imaging system.

The Lucy spacecraft uses tools such as cameras and antennas for many different purposes. There are two cameras on the spacecraft used for OpNav. These are the “L’LORRI”, which is used for long-range reconnaissance, and the “TTCAM” with two thermal imaging cameras. OpNav is used as the spacecraft approaches each Trojan region, so factors such as orbit position and velocity are reanalyzed

and reconstructed. As with all systems, approximately errors will occur before using this navigation system and one of the most important issues is to ensure that these possible errors are corrected before using this system. Geometric distortions found when taking these images are corrected, and the photometric values of the photos are processed and characterized on the Instrument Marking Platform (IPP) in Lucy.

3.7.1 IPP-Gimbal-Angle-Based Instrument Marking Simulator

The characteristics of the “L’LORRI” and “TTCAM” navigation cameras encountered significant difficulties in meeting the IPP requirements. These features included improvements in aspects such as flare sensitivity and aim stability. However, the adjustment system required to ensure that all other requirements are met is very problematic. To identify these issues, an angle-based IPP gimbal tool marking simulator was developed.

3.7.2 L’LORRI’s Equipment

Figure 4: Equipment of the L’LORRI [17]

This camera is the most important one for the mission because it is the most sensitive on the Lucy spacecraft. This is called “eagle eyes.” This panchromatic camera uses a Ritchey-Chréien telescope, similar to the one used by Hubble. The hyperbolic secondary mirror of this telescope reflects light that initially passes through the tube and is reflected by the hyperbolic primary mirror. The secondary mirror focuses the light before it passes through a slit in the primary mirror. In the case of L’LORRI, this happens through different lenses. A device connected to a charger is used to capture the image, and a light-sensitive device is used in digital cameras instead of film.

Figure 5: Diagram of Equipment of the L'LORRI [17]

One of LORRI's goals is to create clear images of Trojan asteroids, even if they are quite dark. LORRI will be able to see craters 70 m in diameter (or 14 m per pixel) at a distance of 1000 km. L'LORRI's fine-grained images allow scientists to better understand the surface geology of Trojan asteroids.

3.8 M. Vertregt, "Orientation in Space" (1956) [8]

Orientation in space must be based on different principles than orientation on Earth, as some orientation systems used on Earth are not applicable in space. For example, on Earth, there are different bodies and shapes that a navigator can use to determine his position and speed and thus acceleration. However, in space, there is usually a piece of light, as well as planets, stars, and various celestial bodies. When they are so far away from the spacecraft, it is difficult to determine their position in space. However, if the reference system is based on the Earth, which has a vernal equinox point and a celestial equator, it is possible to determine the angles of right ascension and declination. However, there are better ways to do this, as the point of the vernal equinox shifts by about 50.3" or more every seventy years. We also know that Earth's orbit precesses. The positions of the stars are therefore constantly changing. The earth's orbit can be chosen as the reference plane, neglecting disturbances. The Earth's tilt is also not constant but decreases by 0.47" per year.

The same approach with Roy works here and continues with orbit determination. By taking the orientation of a reference body and using the Gaussian problem, an orbit can be determined if the orbit elements are known and the orbit is a Kepler orbit. However, since perturbations such as the influence of other bodies must be taken into account, the orbit is no longer Keplerian.

3.9 Wang et al., ” Spacecraft Autonomous Navigation Technologies Based on Multi-Source Information Fusion” (2021) [9]

Space navigation systems cover a variety of tasks, including identifying the spacecraft’s trajectory through space and determining its current position, speed, and distance from Earth.

This category of navigation systems includes three different systems: inertial navigation, autonomous optical navigation, and autonomous pulsar-based navigation.

3.9.1 Inertial Navigation

Inertial navigation uses the spacecraft’s inertia to measure it. Using measuring instruments, the spacecraft can determine the speed and position of the spacecraft. The inertial navigation system has a mechanical system. Advantages include low or no energy consumption during measurements, a high percentage of accurate measurements, and the fact that these systems are highly resistant to damage. For this reason, the inertial navigation system is used not only in space-related situations but also in aviation. The primary disadvantage of this system is that since the inertial navigation system is mechanical, researchers can argue that the mechanisms used will eventually be phased out and become obsolete. However, due to technological developments, these periods are extended by several decades. These are the mechanical systems:

Gyroscope: A gyroscope is essentially a machine that uses the principle of conservation of momentum to determine direction. This mechanism can be divided into two groups. These are gyroscopes with classic mechanics that are built according to the current laws of physics.

Accelerometer: The accelerometer is equipped with a spring system that can determine the acceleration of an object based on the forces acting on the springs and its vibrations.

3.9.2 Autonomous Optical Navigation

The autonomous optical navigation system was developed for space exploration in the 1960s. The researchers applied the integration of this system to tasks. Since AutOpNav is not a mechanical system but is based on an electronic system, since the system includes a computer system, sensors, or a camera system, and these systems are much more open from a development point of view, the desire

to use them in space missions is also becoming deeper and deeper. Additionally, these systems provide the safety net needed to extend spacecraft survivability and durability during space missions.

The principle of operation of AutOpNav is to identify the celestial bodies seen (stars, asteroids, or planets of the solar system) mainly based on the information received, and to determine the movements, distances, and speeds of the celestial bodies found and identified in the images subsequently recorded. After such operations, AutOpNav becomes the main system for determining the speed and position of the spacecraft.

3.9.3 Autonomous Pulsar-Based Navigation

The goal of this autonomous system is to determine the position unit vector of pulsars using very long fundamental interferometry in a barycentric blue reference frame, based on X-rays emitted by pulsars in fast space and the standard arrival time of the X-rays. Compared to a pulsar, the LOS direction and actual arrival time are measured by an X-ray detector on the spacecraft, and an appropriate filtering algorithm is used to obtain navigation information such as the spacecraft's position, speed, and time.

3.10 The AAVSO DSLR Observing Manual [10]

Rather than using photographic film, a digital single-lens reflex camera (also known as a digital SLR or DSLR) combines the optics and mechanisms of a single-lens reflex camera with a digital imaging sensor. The main distinction between a DSLR and other digital cameras is the reflex design approach. The reflex design sends the image to either the viewfinder or the image sensor after light passes through the lens and onto an alternating mirror. The name "single lens" refers to this design because the alternative would be to have a viewfinder with its own lens. Because the viewfinder only uses one lens, the image it displays won't noticeably differ from what the camera's sensor captures.

A combination of optical and electronic parts make up a DSLR camera, which is required for taking pictures. A wealth of settings and in-camera software processing options are also included with many modern DSLR cameras, the majority of which are either completely unhelpful or destructive for astronomical photometry.

A lens fixed to the front of the camera body, a shutter, multiple big filters, a microlens array, extra filters, and a detector make up the camera.

The lens is the first optical element. Projecting and focusing an image onto the sensor is its main function. The f-stop diaphragm is located behind the lens. This

establishes the lens's overall aperture, or light-gathering surface. Usually, the lens body itself houses these elements.

The shutter is usually the first component found inside the camera body. The shutter's function is to regulate the amount of light that enters the camera.

A number of filters that serve various purposes are located behind the shutter, including:

- IR dye which lessens over-sensitivity to infrared and deep red light
- IR cut, a dielectric filter that blocks out infrared wavelengths longer than 700 nm
- UV cut, a dielectric filter that blocks UV radiation shorter than 400 nm
- Low-pass filter that disperses light in order to lessen the Moiré interference pattern brought on by the Bayer structure (which in photometry somewhat affects resolution and the problem of undersampling).

The light falling on each pixel is focused onto its most sensitive area directly in front of the detector and behind these filters by a microlens array that is cemented onto the detector; this increases the filling factor of each pixel to a level that is almost 100%.

There is also a RGB filter called DSLR CMOS (Bayer array). Typically, there are two groups of green pixels. The RGB filters are created by directly applying various pigments to the top surface of every CMOS sensor pixel; these pigments are permanent and cannot be cleaned or removed. As a result, each pixel is only responsive to light of that particular color.

As different camera manufacturers may use different color schemes, it is critical to know which color channel on the DSLR is associated with red, blue, and green.

3.11 R. Armin, "Calibration of a CCD Camera and Correction of Its Images" (1996) [11]

In this project, because some astronomical images are going to be taken calibration of a camera for astronomical images must be done.

For getting data to use for an astronomical aim, the error calculations are really important. Even the pixel size matters in this case. So, the calibration part for the camera is the keystone for astrophotography. In the photography case, the error is called noise. Armin Rest explains the sources of this noise as follows:

- **Readout Noise:** When a photograph taken by a CCD, the camera is collecting and processing the data. In each steps of this data collection and processing it add a noise on it.
- **Background Noise:** The conditions of image like surroundings of it has effect on noise. For example, city lights, moon's condition or the brightness of the sky can be effective. This noises don't effect the brighter ones but has a really countable effect for fainter stars.
- **Processing Noise:** When the output image is going to processed (stacking process) each steps add more noise. For every calibration images, more noise is going to be added, it is independent from the quality of the calibration frames.

To minimize those noises calibration frames are used. Those frames are: Bias, Dark, Flat, and Dark Flat frames. In this project, because of the camera situation, 2 frames were used: Dark and Flat. So, those two frames are going to be explained.

3.11.1 Dark Frames

Even without light, the pixels of the CCD matrix accumulate a signal proportional to the exposure time. The source of this dark or thermal count is the random movement of electrons in the chip. To accurately process a calibrated image, the dark number must be removed.

Apart from the exposure, dark frames are affected by the temperature. So, the dark frames must be taken same temperature where the images are going to be taken.

In conclusion, dark frames must be taken with this path: The camera lens must be covered and must be completely dark, the dark exposure must be the same as the image's exposure and lastly, the darks must have taken the same temperature as the images

3.11.2 Flat Frames

The flat calibration corrects for irregularities in the telescope's FOV and differences in the sensitivity of the CCD itself, the flat frame is a map of the relative sensitivity of each pixel of the detector. They are created by imagining an evenly illuminated surface.

In flat frames, the temperature has no effect on it. So, the flat calibrations can be done anywhere.

In conclusion, flat frames must be taken with this path: The camera must be turned into a completely white place, it can be a full white screen, a full white paper, etc. After that without any exposure, the image must be taken.

After taking those calibration frames, a process called stacking must be done. Stacking is exactly the same with its meaning. The logic behind this process is to put all the images in a row and stack them. This process is made by DeepSkyStacker (DSS) in this project.

There shouldn't be a wrong thought like more calibration frames give more accurate results. Every image increases the noise in the image. For example, consider the noise in the raw signal. The problem is that there is noise not only in the real image but also in the dark and bias. Since all of these sounds come from independent sources, can be determined them using the following equation:

$$N_{S,raw}^2 = F^2 N_{S,real}^2 + N_F^2 S_{real}^2 + N_D^2 + N_B^2 \quad (12)$$

In this project, approximately 20 calibration images were used. Also, after making the stacking process a master image comes out. It is better to use the master images.

3.12 F. Pinto , "CCDs in the mechanics lab—A competitive alternative? (Part I)" (1995) [12]

In this project, some images are going to be taken by a phone camera. Some calculations must be done to better understand this camera and lens. So, in that way, noise calculations can be done. In this paper Fabrizio Pinto giving an equation for calculation distance between two photosites(the distance between adjacent pixel centers):

$$s \approx \frac{\lambda}{F} \quad (13)$$

λ is the wavelength of the light used, and F is the focal length of the camera. With this equation, the lens of the camera can be understood better. For the equipment going to be used in this project which is an iPhone 11, the equation can be solved as :

$$\frac{1.4 \times 10^{-6}}{0.026} \times \frac{180}{\pi} \times 60 = 0.185109(\text{arcminutes}) \quad (14)$$

This equation corresponds for the light itself. Also, lets calculate it for the green color:

$$\frac{1.22 \times 500 \times 10^{-9}}{0.0018} \times \frac{180}{\pi} \times 60 = 1.16501(\text{arcminutes}) \quad (15)$$

This values are going to be leading in the error calculations of the objects coordinates.

4 Methodology

In this project, the JupyterNotebook code that provided by Ahmet Orhun Sivash and his group [6] is going to be used. Apart from that some images are going to be taken by a phone camera (iPhone 11) and DSLR camera, the images are going to be used as data for the position of objects (stars, planets, asteroids) in the code. So, in that way, a more approximate error to the reality for AutoNav can be calculated. To be accurate, the noise in the images must be reduced. For that, some methods as mentioned in sections 3.11 and 3.10 . For that purpose, FOSS programs were used. For this project to make this happen, there is a workflow.

Figure 6: Workflow [18]

4.1 Tools Used

4.1.1 Stellarium

It is a FOSS tool that can be used on the computer. It shows all the space objects like planets, stars, asteroids, etc. The observation coordinates also can be put on Stellarium, that way, the celestial coordinates of objects are going to be really accurate. Stellarium is taking all the celestial elements data from NASA JPL, it is a reliable source.

In that project, Stellarium was used for choosing the observation time, date, and the observation area in the sky. Especially objects that have a magnitude smaller than 8 were chosen because of the capability of the phone. That magnitude of the object and the celestial elements specifically for that time can be found right side of the Stellarium, as can be seen from the figure.

Figure 7: One Part of Stellarium Screen

Magnitude represents the measure of the brightness of any celestial body. Right ascension and declination (RA-DEC) values are the coordinates in astronomy that represents longitude and latitude on Earth.

With respect to Stellarium values, observations are planned due to magnitude and position. Also, the RA-DEC values coming from Stellarium were used for the error calculations.

4.1.2 DeepSkyStacker (DSS)

DeepSky Stacker is a very popular and powerful stacking program widely used by astrophotographers around the world. Better yet, it is free and, thanks to the generosity of its author, available in 12 languages. [19]

It is a FOSS tool for stacking astronomical images with respect to stars rotation and calibration. For calibration process it is using frames as mentioned in Armin Rest's paper.

As can be seen from the screenshot of the DSS the underlined part represents the process that a user process that must be followed. First, as a Light Frame, the images taken must be uploaded. As a Dark Frames, the dark fields taken must be uploaded. As a Flat Frame, the flat fields taken must be uploaded. Then "check all" must be pressed. After that all uploaded images are going to be checked.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker.

After all checked, it seems like exactly in Figure 8. Also, DSS shows the number of frames. At the next stage, the "Register checked pictures" button should be pressed. At the next stage, the "Register checked pictures" button should be pressed. After pressing this, the DSS will ask you about the staking settings.

There are 2 different setting options here. One is recommended settings from DSS itself, and the other one is stacking parameters that can be decided by users.

Figure 9: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker.

In recommended settings, there are some suggestions from DSS, if it is clicked on, DSS will automatically do those settings.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Register Part Settings.

On the other hand, in the Stacking Parameters part, there are lots of options that can be selected. The first part is the result part. Here there are three different options : [19]

- **Standard Mode:** This mode uses a lightweight reference frame to determine the size, orientation, and composition of the final stacked image. The stacked file is the same size as the light frame it references. Only data from each light frame that overlaps the reference light frame is used. The remaining data will be deleted.
- **”Mosaic” Mode:** This mode creates a final image that is a combination of all the stacked light frames. This mode uses all data from stacked light frames; No data will be deleted. The final composite image is physically larger than the photographs and may be a very large file depending on physical size. The size of the stacked image depends on the amount of rotation and movement between images; The more traffic, the larger the file.

Recommended Settings

Figure 11: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Recommended Settings.

- **Intersection Mode:** In the final version, this mode only uses data common to all photographs. This mode removes a lot of information but creates the highest-quality image files. The resulting image is smaller than the light frame. As with mosaic mode, the amount of movement between each image determines the size of the final stacked image. The more movement, the smaller the image and corresponding file size.

In this paper, the Intersection Mode was used.

In this area, there are lots of iteration models for analyzing the data and signals. In this paper for light, Kappa-Sigma clipping was used. DeepSkyStacker calculates the average standard deviation and sigma for all pixels in the stack and rejects all values above a defined multiple of the standard deviation. This is repeated for the selected number of iterations. The multiplicity, kappa, and number of iterations are marked in the boxes to the right of this option.

Figure 12: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Stacking Parameters.

In both Dark and Flat sides "Median Kappa-Sigma clipping" was used. In this method, values are replaced with the median value.

In that section, different output files and different folders for placing can be selected. After all the options part, can click on "OK" and then the process is going to be started.

When the process starts, this screen is going to pop up. On this screen, for every image pieces of information are shown, like rotation angle and offset.

Figure 13: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Stacking Parameters - Light.

When the process and, your image is going to pop up on the screen, and at the bottom part there are lots of points that can change the image. At this point, after pushing "Compute offsets" all data about the images shifting and rotating can be seen.

The rotation angle and the time of the images can be seen. This is going to be important for error calculations of the images that are taken.

Figure 14: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Stacking Parameters - Dark.

Figure 15: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Stacking Parameters - Flat.

After all that process, DSS saves an Autosave.fts file to the folder that where the Light Frames are located. That Autosave.fts file is ready to use as a data

Figure 16: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Stacking Parameters - Output.

Figure 17: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Process.

source. Just before it, with using GIMP[20] the file format must be change to the .fits format.

4.1.3 Astrometry.net [13]

It is a webpage that makes astrometric calibrations for images. After making progress on DSS, images were put on Astrometry.net for calibration. With that technique, the photograph's exact location and the sky's celestial coordinates can be known.

Their approach consists of four main elements. When a query image is ini-

Figure 18: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Output.

Light Frames: 21	Dark Frames: 1	Flat Frames: 1	Dark Flat Frames: 0	Offset/Bias Frames: 0										
					Path	File	Type	Filter	Score	dx	dy	Angle	Date/Tim	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00101.jpeg	Light		58068.05	2.01	11.05	-0.21 °	18.12.2023 21:27:3					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00100.jpeg	Light		176019.32	1.98	-6.97	-0.16 °	18.12.2023 21:27:3					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00099.jpeg	Light		172393.14	1.51	-7.33	-0.09 °	18.12.2023 21:27:4					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00104.jpeg	Light		175693.53	0.53	-6.04	-0.05 °	18.12.2023 21:28:0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00103.jpeg	Light		175731.41	-0.54	-4.06	-0.04 °	18.12.2023 21:28:1					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00102.jpeg	Light		175047.54	-1.04	-1.99	-0.00 °	18.12.2023 21:28:2					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00107.jpeg	Light		181115.75	0.00	0.00	0.00 °	18.12.2023 21:28:4					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00110.jpeg	Light		58550.31	-8.02	22.88	0.18 °	18.12.2023 21:29:4					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00109.jpeg	Light		177562.77	-3.33	7.29	0.19 °	18.12.2023 21:30:0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C:\Users\Monster\Desktop\FENG-497\Observation\2023-12-18\set-3--21-33-14\	image00108.jpeg	Light		173260.78	-5.14	9.07	0.21 °	18.12.2023 21:30:2					

Figure 19: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Offsets.

tially displayed, astronomical sources, commonly referred to as “stars,” are detected through a series of image processing steps, allowing several hundred or more stars to be located with subpixel precision. Subsets of these stars, so-called “quads,” are then examined and a geometric hash code is generated for each subset that describes the relative positions of the stars in the quadrangle. Using these hash codes, the system then searches for nearly identical hash codes in a large pre-computed index, creating hypothetical matches between the squares in the query image and the index. These orientations provide clues to the possible positions, scale, and orientation of the image in the sky. The final element includes a verification criterion formulated as a Bayesian decision problem that efficiently determines the correctness of hypothetical matches. [21]

Geometric hash code sketch for “quad” of stars can be found in the article [22]. It uses 2 different star databases. The first one is the UNSO-B database. USNO-B is a comprehensive celestial catalog presenting positions, proper motions, luminosities in various optical bandwidths, and star/galaxy estimates for 1,042,618,261 objects from 3,643,201,733 individual observations. The data comes from scans of 7,435 Schmidt plates created as part of various sky surveys over the last 50 years. [22]

The second one is Two Micron All Sky Survey. Between June 1997 and February 2001, the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS) collected 25.4 TB of raw image data covering 99.998% of the near-infrared J ($1.25 \mu\text{m}$), H ($1.65 \mu\text{m}$) and K_s ($2.16 \mu\text{m}$).

Edit Image

Submitted by [klymetyldir](#) (43960)
 on 2023-12-29T08:43:43Z
 as "Autosave.jpg" (Submission 8970536)
 under Attribution 3.0 Unported

publicly visible: [yes](#) | [no](#)

Job Status

Job 9696000:
[Success](#)

Calibration

Center (RA, Dec): (88.635, 22.145)
 Center (RA, hms): 05^h 54^m 32.418^s
 Center (Dec, dms): +22° 08' 40.398"
 Size: 74.3 x 55.2 deg
 Radius: 46.281 deg
 Pixel scale: 66.9 arcsec/pixel
 Orientation: Up is 57.1 degrees E of N

WCS file: [wcs.fits](#)
 New FITS image: [new-image.fits](#)
 Reference stars nearby (RA,Dec table): [rdls.fits](#)
 Stars detected in your images (x,y table): [axy.fits](#)
 Correspondences between image and reference stars (table): [corr.fits](#)
 Legacy Surveys sky browser: [browse the sky](#)
 KMZ (Google Sky): [Image.kmz](#)
 World Wide Telescope: [view in WorldWideTelescope](#)

Nearby Images ([View All](#))

Comments

Figure 20: Screenshot of the DeepSkyStacker Offsets.

Figure 21: DeepSkyStacker output for DSLR camera.

Here is the output screen of Astrometry.net. In the "Calibration" area, the middle of the image can be seen as RA-DEC. Also, it provides a FITS form for downloading the calibrated image.

4.1.4 Astrometric Stacking Program (ASTAP)

ASTAP is a FOSS tool, It is capable of stacking images and calculating the RA-DEC values. In this project, ASTAP was used to get the objects' RA-DEC values. Before ASTAP, Astrometry.net made the calibration calculations, like the center of the image as RA-DEC values. With that calibration, ASTAP will be able to calculate every pixel RA-DEC.

Figure 22: Screenshot of the ASTAP.

As underlined in red, the top left part is the center of the image. The bottom part is the RA-DEC value of the exact location where the cursor is located. The left one is the exact location where the cursor is. In the right side part, ASTAP makes a Gaussian approach and calculates the center of the image. In this paper, for calculations, the right side was used.

4.1.5 digiCamControl

It is a FOSS tool that provides to control DSLR camera. The aim behind the use of this tool is to eliminate errors that can be accrued from humans. In the iPhone 11 camera, a remotecontroller was used, but for the DSLR camera, a tool like that is needed. This tool allows one to take pictures without human touch. In this project, this tool was used for the pressing shutter.

Figure 23: Screenshot of the digiCamControl.

Also, digiCamControl allows synchronization of the camera's clock with the computer's. The computer's clock synchronized to the atomic clock with using "time.nist.gov".

4.1.6 Wolfram Language Mathematica

In this paper, for error calculations, the Jupyter Notebook provided by Dr. Fabrizio Pinto was used. The output and the concept will be talked about in the results section.

4.1.7 JPL Horizons System

NASA JPL created the internet tool known as Horizons System. The user of this program can generate outputs to see:

- The ecliptic longitude and the latitude of the target body
- The ecliptic cartesian coordinates of the target body

[6]

and also more can be generated.

ICRF serves as the reference frame for Horizons [23]. An observer on Earth has the choice to ignore the atmospheric impact. The time form and time type are also selectable by the user. As can be seen, all the options are based on the user. In this project, the settings were used with respect to Ahmet Orhun Sivashlı and his team's [6] setup:

- When Observing the Heliocentric Ecliptic Coordinates:
Ephemeris Type: Observer Table
Target Body: Any Celestial Object
Observer Location: @Sun
Time: Time - Type: UT
Table Settings: Options 2, 18 are checked.
Reference Frame: ICRF
Angle Format: Decimal Degrees, Extra Precision: On
CSV Format

- When Observing the Heliocentric Cartesian Coordinates:

Ephemeris Type: Vector Table

Target Body: Any Celestial Object

Observer Location: @Sun

Time: Time - Type: UT

Table Settings: Output Quantities: 1 with XYZ uncertainties.

Reference Frame: ICRF

Reference Plane: ecliptic x-y plane derived from reference frame (standard obliquity, inertial)

Vector Correction: Apparent States

CSV Format

- When Observing the Topocentric Ecliptic and Celestial Coordinates:

Ephemeris Type: Observer Table

Target Body: Any Celestial Object

Observer Location: @ Any Celestial Object

Time: Time - Type: UT

Table Settings: Options 1, 2, 18, 31 are checked. In this project different from them 1 is also checked. 2 refers to Apparent RA and Dec, 1 refers to Astrometric RA and Dec. ASTAP and Stellarium comparisons were made and it was noticed that both of that app uses the first one, so the first one is used in this project.

Reference Frame: ICRF

Angle Format: Decimal Degrees, Extra Precision: On

CSV Format

[6]

More of it can be found on the website [23] of the Horizons System.

4.2 Observation Setup

Every effort was made to reduce human and environmental impacts on the equipment during the observations. A tripod was utilized to steady the camera, and the "digiCamControl" app allowed the camera to be connected to a computer for picture taking. Through the use of this process, images were captured devoid of any direct human involvement. By using these techniques, vibrations may be avoided and precise timing can be obtained by synchronizing the computer and camera with the atomic clock time that the time.is app provides.[18]

Figure 24: DSLR camera setup.

Figure 25: iPhone 11 camera setup.

Of course, image calibration is required for every image that is captured. Without calibration, the results could be impacted by things like dust or an uncontrolled sensor temperature. (See Sec 3.10)[18]

Figure 26: Flat field setup for DSLR camera.

Figure 27: Flat field setup for iPhone camera.

5 Results

5.1 Image Results

After all processes, the final image is these for the iPhone 11 camera and the DSLR camera

Figure 28: Final Image for iPhone 11 camera.

In this image, all constellations can be seen. Also, two important objects for the Orion were shown, the Betelgeuse star and the Orion nebula.

Figure 29: Final Image for DSLR camera.

Figure 30: Final Image for DSLR camera (cropped) (inversed).

Figure 31: Final Image for DSLR camera for a particular area.

5.2 Image Result Analyze

In this project, the aim is to act like the spacecraft is the phone or DSLR camera and analyze the motion errors that could come from the camera. For this motion, the Earth's rotation is going to help us. Also with these data spacecraft position with respect to asteroid observations was going to be calculated.

To understand this rotation, both Stellarium and ASTAP data were used for comparison. Stellarium data is a reliable source because it takes RA-DEC values from NASA JPL. So, in those calculations, Stellarium was used as the true value, ASTAP was used as the calculated value and then error calculations were done. Also, the errors were plotted.

5.2.1 iPhone 11 Result Analyze

Before plots, here is a comparison example.

Figure 32: Screenshot of the ASTAP and Stellarium. (iPhone 11)

The red squares represent the RA-DEC values for each app. These values are compared in the plots.

First with 21 images stacking was made, the errors occurred more than expected. After that, this process was tried with 10 images, and was noticed that the error became less.

Figure 33: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(21 Image)
(iPhone 11)

Figure 34: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(10 Image)
(iPhone 11)

As can be seen from both figures when the number of images that were stacked decreased the error decreased. So to be totally sure, a more different number of images was tried.

Figure 35: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(Both Graph)
(iPhone 11)

Figure 36: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(Density Graph) (iPhone 11)

This is a density plot, here, the background color represents the scalar value of the vectors. In this case, the scalar value means error, so the value goes from dark to bright. That means that darker areas have lower errors than brighter ones.

As can be seen from both figures, there is a difference which cannot be neglectable. After examining the situation, it was understood that these errors occurred as a result of the rotation applied by DSS on the photos during the stacking process. This rotation comes from the Earth's rotation, when the images are taken also time goes on, and as time goes the Earth moves, and the places of objects change. DSS chooses the best frame and rotates other ones according to it.

Figure 37: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(5 Image) (iPhone 11)

Figure 38: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook.(15 Image) (iPhone 11)

The graphs for the 5 images and 15 images look the same, but they are not the same. If looked carefully the difference can be noticeable.

Then a graph that shows the mean error and the standard deviation of the errors was made. In that way, the correlation of the error with the stacked image number can be easily seen.

Figure 39: Mean error and standard deviation graph. (iPhone 11)

As can be seen the mean error and standard deviation graph with respect to the stacked image represents how the stacked image number affects errors. As can be seen, the error increases with respect to the number of stacked images. But there is an expectation for 15 images. As a rumor known by the astrophotography community, as can be seen, the 15 images is the best.

With that error graph, a thought started. Does the time passing through while the observations are done affect the error? Because while the stacking process happens, the DSS finds the stars and rotates all the images with respect to one image that it chooses.

The graph with the time that the images were taken and the rotation angle was done. In that way, the relation between time and rotation can be understandable.

Figure 40: DSS Rotation Graph. (iPhone 11)

As can be seen from the figure, when the time frame increases, the rotation angle that DSS provides also increases.

In this case, understanding this error will help. During the mission, Cube-Sat is going to be moving and rotating in space. While this rotation and motion happening, the navigation must continue.

5.2.2 Nikon D3100 DSLR Camera Result Analyze

The same process was applied to the DSLR camera.

Figure 41: Stacked Image Error Output From JupyterNotebook. (DSLR)

Figure 42: Stacked Image Error Output From Jupyter Notebook.(Density Graph) (DSLR)

As can be seen here, DSS outputs are more accurate than the phone camera due to the equipment. As can be seen here, DSS outputs are more accurate than the phone camera due to the equipment. In the next chapters, the effect of this on the position calculation can be seen. (See sec 5.3)

Figure 43: Mean Error Comparison For Both iPhone and DSLR

With this mean error graph, the difference can be seen more clearly. Due to the equipment, the DSLR camera is 10 times greater than the phone, but the phone still can detect asteroids!

5.3 Implementation of the Image Data to the Software

Thanks to Ahmet Orhun Sivashlı and his team[6], there is a code that implements Roy's[1] and Vergret's[8] equations for the beacon asteroids and makes us find to position of the spacecraft, in this case, the observation center.

Figure 44: The Model of Optical Navigation (Sketched via diagrams.net)[1]

$$r = r_P \frac{\cos \beta_P \sin(\lambda_P - \lambda'_P)}{\cos \beta_S \sin(\lambda'_P - \lambda'_S)}$$

RED: Known From Ephemeris
 BLUE: From Astrometric Observations
 GREEN: From Astrometric Observations and Sensor (here from ephemeris)

Heliocentric latitude of the asteroid
 Heliocentric longitude of the asteroid
 Topocentric longitude of the asteroid
 Topocentric latitude of the Sun
 Topocentric longitude of the asteroid
 Topocentric longitude of the Sun

Figure 45: The Equation of Optical Navigation (Sketched via diagrams.net)[1]

In the equation, red ones are already known from ephemeris that are produced by NASA JPL. In the real mission, they can be implemented on the flight computer. Blue ones are the observation outputs, calculated by taking photos and will be calculated by taking photos in a real mission. Green ones are also the observation outputs or a sun sensor. But in this case, it is ephemeris because there is no necessary equipment. In real missions, it can be either observation or a sun sensor. By putting this information in the equation, the position of the spacecraft was calculated. As said, the position of the spacecraft was the observation center which is İzmir, Çeşme.

During the position calculation, also the reference frame corrections must have been done. Thanks to Ahmet Orhan Sivashlı and his team's [6] code, this was also implemented.

Figure 46: Reference Frame Calculation (Sketched via diagrams.net)

This error has also been added to prevent any additional errors.

Figure 47: Output of of the Code that Calculates Position of the Spacecraft.

As can be seen from the graph, the position of the spacecraft, which is the observation center Çeşme, calculated with respect to observation output RA and Dec values.

The observation values are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RA (Right ascension)} &= 6\text{h } 12\text{m } 00.04\text{s} \\ \text{Dec(Declination)} &= +24^\circ 44' 27.4'' \end{aligned}$$

The expected values are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RA (Right ascension)} &= 6\text{h } 12\text{m } 02.33\text{s} \\ \text{Dec(Declination)} &= +24^\circ 44' 37.7'' \end{aligned}$$

As can be seen, there are errors between the observation and expected values due to the equipment and atmospheric conditions. These errors affect the position calculation.

Now let's take a look at the error between the expected position of the spacecraft and the calculated position of the spacecraft.

Errors in Axis:

X Axis: 238427 km

Y Axis: 91651 km

Z Axis: 10 km

Error in magnitude:

r Spacecraft Error: -255435 km

Error ratio:

r Measured: 255435 km

Distance Between Earth-Sun : 149×10^8 km

Relative Error: $\frac{255435}{149 \times 10^8 km}$

Relative Error: 0.000017

As can be seen from the upside, the relative error is small with respect to the position of the Earth to the Sun. Optical navigation which uses asteroids as beacons is possible with a small lens camera due to the calculations.

6 Next Steps

As the next steps, more asteroid implementation is aimed. Implementation of the Kalman Filter is also aimed. Kalman filter is really important for increasing the predictions and making it more accurate.

In the figure on page 58 in article [24], navigation uncertainties of Viking 1 can be seen. The number of the ellipses shows the number of days after launch. For example in the first week, The error is so big that it does not even fit in the photo. But day by day, it decreases and gets smaller and smaller. With that approach, a journey to Mars can be done with minimal error.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, in this paper, the mission that Hazal Karaaliler and her team [5] started and Ahmet Orhun Sivaslı and his team [6] developed, continued. In this case, the optical navigation part of the mission getting more realistic. Observations have been done. In that way, it assumes that the iPhone 11 's camera and DSLR camera is a spacecraft and the rotation of the Earth is the simulation of the movement of the spacecraft. The calculation of the position of the spacecraft, in this case is observation center, has been done. Understanding the errors of the rotation will lead to calculating the position of the spacecraft more accurately.

It is possible to use a small lens camera on CubeSat to make autonomous optical navigation. The relative error is 0.000017, which is acceptable, also with usage of the Kalman filter, error can decrease more. [24]

Trying to develop more accurate optical autonomous navigation is a capstone for space missions. The load of the DSN is very high. It is going to be a problem for all the missions. On the other hand, space missions become more interesting for deep space, because deep space is mysterious still today and even observing it is difficult. In this century deep space missions getting on top. In this kind of mission, Earth-based navigation becomes difficult because of the long distances. Autonomous navigation become important and needs to be developed for these kinds of missions. The solar-sail technology makes these deep space missions possible. It makes it possible to get on high velocity without any traditional propulsion technology. It can handle the necessary energy without using heavy and large fuel tanks.

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